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Comparative in Vitro Study of the Antibacterial Effect of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. Seed and Leaf on Bacteria Associated with Urinary Tract Infections

Akubuo Chigaemezu Remmy-Martin¹, Okorocho Bright Odinaka^{2,3,*}, James Onyedikachi Ani⁴, Odia Alex Osaro⁵, and Edwin Agbeze⁶

¹ Department of Microbiology, Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

² Department of Medicine and Surgery, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria

³ Person-Centered HIV Research Team, Department of Clinical Pharmacy and Pharmacy Management, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria

⁴ Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto State, Nigeria

⁵ Department of Chemical Sciences, Faculty of Science, University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria

⁶ Department of Pharmacy, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State Nigeria

*E-mail address: Brightodinaka76@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) remain a major global health concern, increasingly complicated by antimicrobial resistance. *Moringa oleifera* Lam. is a widely used medicinal plant with documented antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, yet comparative evaluations of its leaf and seed antibacterial activities remain limited. This study investigated and compared the in vitro antibacterial effects of ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *M. oleifera* leaves and seeds against common uropathogenic bacteria. Extracts were prepared by maceration in ethanol and distilled water. Antibacterial activity was assessed using agar well diffusion and broth microdilution techniques against *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Minimum inhibitory (MIC) and bactericidal (MBC) concentrations were determined. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Pearson correlation. Ethanolic extracts exhibited significantly higher antibacterial activity than aqueous extracts ($p < 0.05$). The ethanolic leaf extract produced the

largest inhibition zones (18-23 mm) and lowest MIC values (15.63-31.25 mg/mL), particularly against *Klebsiella* and *Proteus* spp. The ethanolic seed extract showed notable activity against *S. aureus* (MIC: 31.25 mg/mL). A strong negative correlation ($r = -0.86$, $p < 0.01$) was observed between inhibition zones and MICs, confirming consistency between diffusion and dilution assays. Ethanolic extracts of *M. oleifera* leaves and seeds demonstrate broad-spectrum antibacterial efficacy, supporting their potential as natural alternatives or adjuncts in managing UTIs. Further isolation, purification, and clinical validation of the active constituents are warranted to develop standardized phytotherapeutic agents.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, urinary tract infection, antibacterial activity, MIC, MBC, phytochemistry, antibiotic resistance

1. INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) remain among the most common bacterial infections globally, posing a persistent public health challenge that affects millions of individuals each year. They occur across all age groups and both sexes but are particularly frequent in women due to anatomical and physiological predispositions (Bono & Leslie, 2025). The majority of community-acquired infections are caused by uropathogenic *Escherichia coli*, which accounts for more than 70% of cases, while *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Enterobacter* spp., *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are frequently implicated in complicated or recurrent infections. Beyond their prevalence, UTIs are clinically significant because of their tendency to recur and their potential to progress to pyelonephritis or sepsis. The increasing emergence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) among uropathogens has further complicated treatment outcomes and limited the effectiveness of commonly prescribed antibiotics (World Health Organization, 2023).

The rise of AMR has become a critical concern in UTI management worldwide. In many low- and middle-income countries, including Nigeria, the problem is magnified by widespread self-medication, the unregulated sale of antibiotics, and economic barriers that limit access to effective treatment options. Consequently, attention has shifted toward identifying affordable, safe, and locally available therapeutic alternatives. Medicinal plants, long used in traditional healing systems, have gained renewed interest as potential sources of bioactive compounds with antimicrobial activity. Their accessibility, cultural acceptance, and relatively low toxicity make them promising candidates for the development of complementary or alternative antimicrobial therapies.

Moringa oleifera, commonly known as the drumstick or miracle tree, is one such plant with a well-documented history of ethnomedicinal use across tropical and subtropical regions (Pareek et al., 2023). Every part of the plant—the leaves, seeds, bark, flowers, and pods—has been employed in folk medicine for treating infections, inflammation, and malnutrition.

The pharmacological interest in *M. oleifera* lies in its diverse phytochemical composition. The leaves are rich in flavonoids such as quercetin and kaempferol, phenolic acids including chlorogenic and ferulic acids, and a range of vitamins and minerals that contribute to their antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (El-Sherbiny et al., 2024; Ahmed et al., 2023).

The seeds, in contrast, contain benzyl isothiocyanates and water-soluble lectins that exhibit potent antibacterial effects by disrupting microbial membranes, inhibiting biofilm

formation, and interfering with bacterial cell survival (Moura et al., 2015). Experimental evidence supports these claims. El-Sherbiny et al. (2024) demonstrated that ethanolic extracts of *M. oleifera* leaves significantly inhibited the growth of *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*, while Ahmed et al. (2023) observed strong antimicrobial activity in both aqueous and ethanolic extracts. Similarly, Padla et al. (2012) isolated isothiocyanates from seeds with broad-spectrum antibacterial effects, and Moura et al. (2015) described a seed lectin capable of altering bacterial membrane integrity. More recently, Apenteng-Takyiako et al. (2025) compared the antibacterial profiles of seed and leaf extracts against multidrug-resistant clinical isolates, reporting that both possess inhibitory activity, though with variable potency depending on the bacterial species. Nonetheless, van den Berg and Kuipers (2022) noted inconsistencies across published data, often arising from variations in extraction protocols, solvent polarity, and testing methodologies.

Given the escalating threat of antibiotic resistance and the extensive traditional use of *M. oleifera* in local medicine, a comparative in-vitro evaluation of the antibacterial activity of its seeds and leaves against UTI-associated pathogens is both timely and necessary. This study seeks to determine which plant part exhibits greater antibacterial potential and to provide scientific validation for traditional therapeutic claims. By targeting key uropathogens such as *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *Proteus* spp., the research aims to contribute to evidence-based strategies for integrating phytomedicine into mainstream antimicrobial therapy, particularly in resource-limited settings.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The study was carried out at the Federal University Teaching Hospital, Owerri (FUTHO) a major tertiary healthcare and referral facility serving Imo State and neighboring regions of southeastern Nigeria. Owerri, the capital of Imo State, is geographically situated between latitudes 6°03'51" and 7°02'81" N and longitudes 5°01'00" and 6°00'01" E. The city encompasses three Local Government Areas (Owerri Municipal, Owerri North, and Owerri West) with an estimated population of over 400,000 people according to the 2006 national census. The hospital's well-equipped diagnostic microbiology laboratory provided an appropriate environment for this laboratory-based investigation.

2. 2. Materials

The following materials were used for the study: sterile cotton swabs, Petri dishes, glass slides, cover slips, test tubes, conical flasks, inoculating loops and needles, autoclave, hot-air oven, Bunsen burner, rotary evaporator, mortar and pestle/electric grinder, Whatman No. 1 filter paper, aluminum foil, and standard culture media. Standard antibiotic discs (ciprofloxacin, nitrofurantoin, and amoxicillin-clavulanate) served as positive controls.

2. 2. 1. Reagents

Distilled water was used for media preparation and cleaning. Ethanol (95%) served as the extraction solvent, and 5% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used to dissolve extracts during antibacterial assays. McFarland 0.5 turbidity standard was employed to standardize bacterial inocula.

2. 3. Culture Media and Preparation

Mueller–Hinton agar (MHA) was employed for antibacterial susceptibility testing as recommended by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, 2017) because of its consistent composition and ability to support most non-fastidious pathogens. Media were prepared according to manufacturer’s instructions, sterilized at 121 °C for 15 min, and poured aseptically into sterile Petri dishes (15-20 mL per plate). The plates were allowed to solidify, inverted to prevent condensation, and stored at 4 °C until use (Ohazuruike et al., 2017).

2. 4. Sterilization and Aseptic Procedures

All glassware was washed, rinsed, and sterilized in a hot-air oven at 160 °C for 2 h. Culture media and other heat-resistant materials were autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min. Inoculating loops and needles were flamed to red-hot before and after each use. Working surfaces were disinfected with 75% ethanol, and aseptic manipulations were performed near a lit Bunsen burner to maintain an upward air current that minimized airborne contamination (Ohazuruike et al., 2017).

2. 5. Bacterial Isolates

Clinical isolates of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., and *Staphylococcus aureus* were obtained from the Microbiology Department of FUTHO. These isolates had been previously identified and confirmed by standard biochemical and morphological methods.

2. 6. Preparation of Plant Materials and Extracts

Fresh leaves and mature seeds of *Moringa oleifera* were collected from Owerri, Imo State. The samples were rinsed in distilled water, shade-dried at room temperature (10-14 days), and pulverized into fine powder using a sterile electric grinder.

Two solvent systems were used:

- **Aqueous extraction:** 100 g of leaf or seed powder was soaked in 500 mL of distilled water for 72 h with intermittent shaking, filtered through Whatman No. 1 paper, and concentrated at 50 °C using a water bath.
- **Ethanolic extraction:** 100 g of powdered sample was soaked in 500 mL of 95% ethanol for 72 h, filtered, and concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 40-45 °C.

The crude extracts were stored in sterile airtight containers at 4 °C. Stock solutions (100 mg/mL) were prepared in 5% DMSO for use in antibacterial testing (Pareek et al., 2023; El-Sherbiny et al., 2024; Tama, 2024).

2. 7. Antibacterial Susceptibility Testing

The antibacterial activity of aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *M. oleifera* leaves and seeds was assessed using the Kirby–Bauer disc diffusion method on MHA plates, following CLSI (2017) standards.

Bacterial suspensions were standardized to the 0.5 McFarland turbidity ($\approx 1 \times 10^8$ CFU/mL). Sterile 6 mm discs were impregnated with extract concentrations of 25, 50, 75, 100, and 125 mg/mL and placed on inoculated MHA plates.

- **Positive controls:** ciprofloxacin, nitrofurantoin, and amoxicillin–clavulanate discs
- **Negative control:** sterile distilled water

Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h, and zones of inhibition were measured (mm) using a digital Vernier caliper. All tests were performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility (Apenteng-Takyiako et al., 2025; Jahan et al., 2022).

2. 8. Determination of Minimum Inhibitory and Bactericidal Concentrations

2. 8. 1. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

MICs were determined by the broth microdilution method. Serial two-fold dilutions (125 – 12.5 mg/mL) of each extract were prepared in nutrient broth. Each tube received 1 mL of standardized bacterial suspension. Tubes were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h, and the MIC was recorded as the lowest extract concentration showing no visible turbidity compared with controls (Humphries et al., 2018).

2. 8. 2. Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

Aliquots (0.1 mL) from clear MIC tubes were sub-cultured on MHA plates and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The MBC was defined as the lowest concentration showing complete absence of bacterial growth, representing $\geq 99.9\%$ killing of the initial inoculum (El-Sherbiny et al., 2024; Panova et al., 2025).

2. 8. 3. Interpretation

The MBC/MIC ratio was used to classify extract activity: ratios ≤ 4 indicated bactericidal, and > 4 indicated bacteriostatic effects (Tama, 2024).

2. 9. Data Analysis

Experimental results (zones of inhibition, MIC, and MBC values) were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) from three independent replicates. Data visualization (bar charts, tables) illustrated differences in antibacterial activity between extracts, solvents, and bacterial species. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics v26.0. Differences between mean inhibition zones were evaluated using one-way ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post-hoc test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Antibacterial Activity of *Moringa oleifera* Extracts

The antibacterial activity of *Moringa oleifera* leaf and seed extracts was evaluated against *Pseudomonas* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Ethanol extracts demonstrated significantly higher inhibition zones than aqueous extracts ($p < 0.05$).

The ethanolic leaf extract showed the greatest inhibition against *Klebsiella* spp. (23 mm) and *Proteus* spp. (20 mm), while ethanolic seed extracts were most effective against *S. aureus* (15 mm at 125 mg/mL). Aqueous extracts showed minimal or no activity. Among the controls, ciprofloxacin produced the largest inhibition zones (24-30 mm) across all isolates, validating

the assay performance, followed by nitrofurantoin and amoxicillin–clavulanate. Sterile water produced no inhibitory effect.

All assays were performed in triplicate, and results were reproducible with < 5% variation between replicates. Values are expressed as mean ± SD (Tables 1-2; Figure 1). The quantitative antibacterial potency, represented by minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values, is shown in Figure 2.

Ethanol leaf extracts had the lowest MICs (15.63-31.25 mg/mL) against *Proteus* and *Klebsiella* spp., indicating greater efficacy than seed or aqueous extracts ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1. Zones of inhibition (mm) of *Moringa oleifera* seed extracts against UTI pathogens.

Extract (Seed)	Conc. (mg/mL)	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	<i>Proteus</i> spp.	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
Ethanol	25	7.0 ± 0.3 ^a	9.0 ± 0.2 ^a	6.0 ± 0.2 ^a	7.0 ± 0.3 ^a	10.0 ± 0.4 ^a
	50	9.0 ± 0.4 ^a	11.0 ± 0.5 ^a	7.0 ± 0.2 ^a	8.0 ± 0.3 ^a	12.0 ± 0.5 ^a
	75	10.0 ± 0.5 ^b	12.0 ± 0.5 ^b	8.0 ± 0.3 ^b	9.0 ± 0.4 ^b	13.0 ± 0.6 ^b
	100	11.0 ± 0.6 ^b	13.0 ± 0.5 ^b	8.0 ± 0.3 ^b	10.0 ± 0.4 ^b	14.0 ± 0.6 ^b
	125	11.0 ± 0.6 ^b	13.0 ± 0.5 ^b	8.0 ± 0.3 ^b	10.0 ± 0.4 ^b	15.0 ± 0.8 ^c
Water (25–125)	–	–	–	–	–	–
Controls	Ciprofloxacin (5 µg): 25-30 mm	Nitrofurantoin (300 µg): 18-21 mm	Amoxicillin–clavulanate (20/10 µg): 14-18 mm	Sterile water: –		

Different superscripts (^a, ^b, ^c) indicate significant differences among means at $p < 0.05$ (ANOVA, Tukey’s HSD).

Table 2. Zones of inhibition (mm) of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts against UTI pathogens.

Extract (Leaf)	Conc. (mg/mL)	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	<i>Proteus</i> spp.	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
Ethanol	25	9.0 ± 0.3 ^a	15.0 ± 0.7 ^a	18.0 ± 0.9 ^a	7.0 ± 0.3 ^a	–
	50	11.0 ± 0.5 ^a	17.0 ± 0.8 ^b	20.0 ± 0.9 ^b	8.0 ± 0.3 ^a	–
	75	12.0 ± 0.6 ^b	19.0 ± 0.8 ^b	22.0 ± 1.1 ^b	8.5 ± 0.4 ^b	–
	100	13.0 ± 0.7 ^b	20.0 ± 0.9 ^b	23.0 ± 1.2 ^c	9.0 ± 0.2 ^b	–
	125	13.0 ± 0.7 ^b	20.0 ± 0.9 ^b	23.0 ± 1.2 ^c	9.0 ± 0.2 ^b	–

Water	25	8.0 ± 0.3 ^a	9.0 ± 0.3 ^a	–	7.0 ± 0.2 ^a	–
	50	9.0 ± 0.4 ^a	10.0 ± 0.4 ^a	–	8.0 ± 0.3 ^a	–
	75	10.0 ± 0.5 ^b	11.0 ± 0.5 ^b	–	8.5 ± 0.4 ^b	–
	100	11.0 ± 0.4 ^b	11.0 ± 0.5 ^b	–	9.0 ± 0.3 ^b	–
	125	11.0 ± 0.4 ^b	11.0 ± 0.5 ^b	–	9.0 ± 0.3 ^b	–
Ciprofloxacin (5 µg)	–	25.0 ± 1.2	28.0 ± 1.1	24.0 ± 0.9	26.0 ± 1.0	30.0 ± 1.3
Nitrofurantoin (300 µg)	–	19.0 ± 0.8	20.0 ± 0.7	18.0 ± 0.9	19.0 ± 0.8	21.0 ± 0.9
Amoxicillin-clavulanate (20/10 µg)	–	15.0 ± 0.7	17.0 ± 0.8	14.0 ± 0.6	16.0 ± 0.7	18.0 ± 0.8
Sterile Water	–	–	–	–	–	–

Different superscripts (a, b, c) indicate significant differences among means at $p < 0.05$ (ANOVA, Tukey's HSD).

Figure 1. Comparative bar chart of inhibition zones (mean ± SD) for ethanolic and aqueous *Moringa oleifera* leaf and seed extracts against UTI pathogens (*Pseudomonas* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *E. coli*, *S. aureus*). Error bars represent standard deviation from triplicate experiments; $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Heat map of MIC values (mg/mL) for ethanolic and aqueous *M. oleifera* leaf and seed extracts against UTI pathogens. Cells show numerical MICs; darker shades indicate lower MICs (greater potency). Significance assessed at $p < 0.05$.

3. 2. Minimum Inhibitory and Bactericidal Concentrations

MIC and MBC assays confirmed the higher potency of ethanolic extracts (Table 3). The ethanolic leaf extract exhibited the lowest MICs (15.63 mg/mL) against *Proteus* spp. and *Klebsiella* spp., while the ethanolic seed extract showed notable activity against *S. aureus* (31.25 mg/mL). Aqueous extracts displayed minimal inhibition (≥ 62.5 mg/mL). Ciprofloxacin showed MICs between 0.25-1.0 mg/mL. MBC/MIC ratios ≤ 4 indicated bactericidal action. All assays were performed in triplicate and yielded consistent results with $< 5\%$ variation between replicates. Values are expressed as mean \pm SD (Table 3; Figures 3 and 4).

Table 3. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values (mg/mL) of *Moringa oleifera* leaf and seed extracts against UTI pathogens.

Extract Source	Solvent	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	<i>Proteus</i> spp.	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
Seed	Ethanol	62.5 / 125	31.25 / 62.5	62.5 / 125	31.25 / 62.5	31.25 / 62.5
	Water	- / -	- / -	- / -	- / -	- / -

Leaves	Ethanol	31.25 / 62.5	15.63 / 31.25	15.63 / 31.25	31.25 / 62.5	- / -
	Water	62.5 / 125	62.5 / 125	- / -	62.5 / 125	- / -
Ciprofloxacin		0.25 / 0.5	0.25 / 0.5	0.5 / 1.0	0.25 / 0.5	0.25 / 0.5

MIC = minimum inhibitory concentration; MBC = minimum bactericidal concentration; “-” = no inhibition.

Figure 3. Heat map of MIC values (mg/mL) for ethanolic and aqueous *M. oleifera* leaf and seed extracts against UTI pathogens. Cells display numerical MIC values; darker shades represent lower MICs (indicating greater antibacterial potency). Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$.

3. 3. Statistical Summary and Correlation Analysis

A comparative statistical visualization (Figure 5 and 6) was developed to summarize the antibacterial efficacy of ethanolic and aqueous *Moringa oleifera* leaf and seed extracts across all test pathogens. The ethanolic leaf extract produced the greatest mean inhibition ($\approx 18.5 \pm 0.9$ mm), significantly higher than the ethanolic seed extract ($\approx 11.4 \pm 0.6$ mm; $p < 0.05$). Aqueous extracts of both plant parts displayed weak activity (< 10 mm). These differences were statistically significant according to one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 4. Heat map of MBC values (mg/mL) for ethanolic and aqueous *M. oleifera* leaf and seed extracts against UTI pathogens. Darker colors indicate lower MBC values and thus stronger bactericidal activity. All assays were performed in triplicate and values are presented as mean \pm SD ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 5. Comparative antibacterial efficacy of *Moringa oleifera* leaf and seed extracts. Mean inhibition zones (\pm SD) for ethanolic and aqueous extracts against pooled uropathogenic isolates are shown. Error bars represent standard deviations from triplicate determinations; $p < 0.05$.

Figure 6. Correlation between inhibition zone diameters and minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of *Moringa oleifera* extracts. Scatter plot with linear regression line illustrating the inverse relationship between zone diameter and MIC value, confirming higher potency of ethanolic extracts.

A Pearson correlation analysis between inhibition zone diameters and corresponding MIC values revealed a strong inverse relationship ($r = -0.86$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that larger inhibition zones were associated with lower MIC values (greater antibacterial potency). This confirms the internal consistency between agar diffusion and broth dilution results and supports the robustness of the observed antibacterial trends.

3. 4. Results Overview

Overall, both qualitative and quantitative assays demonstrated that *Moringa oleifera* extracts possess notable antibacterial activity against common uropathogens, with ethanol proving to be a superior solvent for bioactive compound extraction. The ethanolic leaf extract consistently produced the widest inhibition zones and lowest MIC and MBC values, indicating potent bactericidal properties, particularly against *Proteus* and *Klebsiella* species. The ethanolic seed extract showed moderate efficacy, most pronounced against *Staphylococcus aureus*, while aqueous extracts were largely inactive. Statistical analyses confirmed significant differences between extracts ($p < 0.05$), and correlation studies revealed a strong negative association between inhibition zone diameter and MIC values ($r = -0.86$, $p < 0.01$). These findings collectively validate the consistency between diffusion and dilution methods and underscore the therapeutic potential of *M. oleifera* as a source of effective antibacterial agents for urinary tract infections.

4. DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates that ethanolic extracts of *Moringa oleifera* leaves and seeds possess significant antibacterial activity against common urinary-tract pathogens, including *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Ethanolic preparations showed larger inhibition zones and lower MIC/MBC values than aqueous extracts, emphasizing the decisive role of solvent polarity in releasing bioactive constituents. Similar solvent-dependent patterns have been documented in earlier phytochemical investigations, where ethanol or methanol extracted phenolic acids, flavonoids, alkaloids, and isothiocyanates more efficiently than water (Pareek et al., 2023; Anzano et al., 2022; Kashyap et al., 2022; Fitri et al., 2025).

Among all extracts tested, the ethanolic leaf extract exerted the most pronounced effect, particularly against *Klebsiella* and *Proteus* species, both of which are clinically relevant causes of recurrent and complicated UTIs. Comparable activity was reported by El-Sherbiny et al. (2024), who found that ethanolic *M. oleifera* leaves inhibited several Gram-negative isolates more effectively than aqueous preparations. The stronger efficacy of ethanolic extracts is largely attributed to their enrichment in polyphenolic compounds such as quercetin and kaempferol, which possess membrane-disruptive and enzyme-inhibitory properties. Ndhlala et al. (2014) similarly concluded that variability in solvent extraction accounts for substantial differences in antibacterial potency among *M. oleifera* studies.

Seed extracts displayed moderate but consistent activity, most notably against *S. aureus*, corroborating findings by Moura et al. (2015), who characterized a water-soluble seed lectin (WSMoL) capable of disrupting bacterial cell membranes and impairing biofilm formation. Although seeds generally contain lower total phenolic content than leaves, the presence of benzyl isothiocyanate and lectin-like proteins likely contributes to their specific activity against Gram-positive bacteria. Collectively, these results highlight that different anatomical parts of *M. oleifera* may act through complementary mechanisms, extending its spectrum of action.

The enhanced efficacy of ethanolic extracts can be linked to their diverse phytochemical profile. *M. oleifera* leaves are rich in chlorogenic and ferulic acids, flavonoids, tannins, and glucosinolates that exert bactericidal effects by damaging bacterial membranes, destabilizing peptidoglycan layers, and interfering with DNA and protein synthesis (van den Berg & Kuipers, 2022). Phenolic acids can also chelate transition metals, depriving bacteria of cofactors needed for oxidative metabolism, while flavonoids perturb membrane permeability. Seeds contribute additional isothiocyanates that generate reactive oxygen species, leading to cell lysis (Moura et al., 2015).

The strong inverse correlation observed between inhibition zones and MIC values ($r = -0.86$, $p < 0.01$) reinforces the internal validity of our data: extracts diffusing better in agar also exhibited higher potency in broth microdilution. This consistency mirrors results reported by Apenteng-Takyiako et al. (2025), who demonstrated that inhibition-zone diameter and MIC were tightly coupled when testing *M. oleifera* leaf extracts against multidrug-resistant hospital isolates.

Antimicrobial resistance among uropathogens remains a major global concern. The World Health Organization's GLASS report (2023) highlights rising resistance of *E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* to fluoroquinolones and β -lactams, reducing treatment options in low-resource settings. Within this context, the broad-spectrum bactericidal activity of *M. oleifera* ethanolic extracts observed here suggests genuine translational promise.

Maurya & Singh (2014) reported that clinical administration of *M. oleifera* stem-bark extract to UTI patients significantly alleviated symptoms and reduced microbial counts, supporting the therapeutic relevance of our in-vitro findings.

Beyond direct antimicrobial effects, *M. oleifera* exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties that could aid tissue healing during infection (Paul & Didia, 2012; Stohs & Hartman, 2015). These pharmacodynamic synergies imply that *M. oleifera* could serve both as a bactericidal and a host-protective agent, warranting further pharmacokinetic and toxicity evaluation.

From a socio-economic viewpoint, *Moringa oleifera* is abundant, inexpensive, and culturally accepted across tropical regions, making it a feasible candidate for community-based antimicrobial programs. Integrating standardized *M. oleifera* formulations into primary-healthcare frameworks could reduce reliance on costly synthetic antibiotics and mitigate resistance driven by their misuse. Nutritionally, the plant's high content of micronutrients (iron, calcium, and vitamins A and C) may reinforce host immunity, a concept often termed "nutritional immunity." The dual antimicrobial and nutritional potential of *M. oleifera* thus represents a sustainable approach to infection control in low- and middle-income countries.

5. CONCLUSION

This study provides robust experimental evidence that ethanolic extracts of *Moringa oleifera* leaves and seeds possess potent, broad-spectrum antibacterial activity against key uropathogens, notably *Klebsiella* spp., *Proteus* spp., *E. coli*, and *S. aureus*. The superior performance of ethanolic over aqueous extracts underscores the importance of solvent polarity in optimizing phytochemical yield and bioactivity. The low MIC and MBC values observed coupled with a strong inverse correlation between inhibition zones and MICs confirm the extracts' genuine bactericidal potential rather than merely inhibitory effects. The antimicrobial efficacy observed here is likely driven by a synergistic interplay of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and isothiocyanates, which act through multiple mechanisms including membrane disruption, oxidative stress induction, and interference with bacterial replication. These findings reinforce the biochemical rationale for *M. oleifera* as a credible natural antibacterial agent.

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